

A coupled virtual element-interface model for analysis of fracture propagation in polycrystalline composites

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a coupled virtual element-interface finite element model for the analysis of the fracture propagation in polycrystalline composites with random microstructure. The key idea is to discretize each crystal, also referred to as grain, with a single low order virtual element with elastic constitutive response, and describe the interaction between grains by means of damaging and frictional zero-thickness interface finite elements. Thus, the typical intergranular crack growth is modeled by avoiding refined finite element grain discretizations with relevant computational cost saving. Results of numerical simulations are presented and discussed. First, some benchmarks show the reliability of the proposed modeling strategy. Then, the response of Alumina/Zirconia representative volume elements, whose size is selected on the basis of results of a statistical homogenization procedure tailored for random composites, is investigated by analyzing the effect of the variation of the metallic phase volume fraction and the shape of grains composing the microstructure.

1. Introduction

Ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) are a special class of materials, comprising ceramic particles or short/long fibers dispersed within a ceramic matrix, which can also include polycrystalline or layered structures. These composites are engineered to overcome the limitations commonly observed in conventional ceramics used in various technical applications, particularly concerning their brittle-like fracture under mechanical or thermal stresses [1]. The inclusion of ceramic particles or fibers enhances fracture toughness, potentially transitioning the brittle response to a more ductile fracture behavior and improving the material resistance to thermal shock. Moreover, CMCs retain the advantageous properties of the ceramic matrix, such as high strength and Young's modulus.

In addition to their increased fracture toughness and resistance to thermal shock, CMCs also exhibit excellent properties of corrosion resistance and high temperature endurance. Their capability to maintain mechanical properties at extreme temperatures makes them ideal for high-temperature and high-pressure environments. Furthermore, CMCs can be designed to have a lighter specific weight compared to metallic materials, offering significant advantages in the aerospace and automotive applications, where weight is a critical factor [2–5]. The corrosion resistance is important, especially in aggressive environments such as marine or chemically reactive ones, where long-term durability is crucial. Additionally, the dimensional stability of CMCs, combined with their wear and fatigue resistance, makes them suitable for high dynamic load applications, such as rotating components in high-performance machinery. Hence, the applications of CMCs are manifold and encompass critical areas such as heat shield

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systems for space vehicles, brake disks, slide bearings, components for high-temperature gas turbines, cutting tools, and burner components [6–9].

An outstanding prototype of polycrystalline CMC is undeniably the Alumina and phase-stabilized Zirconia composite $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2$ (with varying volume contents), as discussed in [10]. This composite merges the favorable features of Alumina, such as high hardness and low susceptibility to aging, and Zirconia, namely high fracture toughness and resistance to subcritical crack growth [5,11].

The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2$ composite is characterized by a complex internal arrangement composed of Alumina and Zirconia grains with dimensions varying from 0.2 μm to 2 μm . A cluster of randomly dispersed grains forms a polycrystalline structure. Its mechanical characterization has garnered considerable attention within the scientific community, as evidenced by [12–18], with the primary objective of designing optimized materials capable of meeting high-tech demands.

Relying on the above considerations, this paper focuses on the nonlinear response of Alumina/Zirconia Representative Volume Elements (RVEs), considering the influence of different volume content of the two components and accounting for the effect of the microstructure randomness. Specifically, we propose an efficient and reliable nonlinear model that merges Virtual Elements (VEs) and Interface Finite Elements (IFEs), aiming to reduce computational burden although preserving accuracy.

The Virtual Element Method (VEM) is a numerical procedure [19,20] developed in recent years as a viable alternative to the Finite Element Method (FEM), for a broad spectrum of mechanical applications [21–26]. The method has recently been enhanced [27,28] and extended to perform large displacement analysis within the corotational framework [29,30]. Its peculiar features, in terms of high flexibility in the number of nodes and shape of elements, make it suitable for modeling materials with polycrystalline microstructures [31,32], as each grain can be discretized with just one virtual element with generic shape. However, it should be mentioned that the literature also proposed other methods capable of managing polygonal elements to mimic the natural shape of each grain, such as Polygonal Finite Elements [33–37], Voronoi cell Finite Elements [38–41], and Trefftz–Lekhnitskii Grains [42].

Interface elements have been employed in many engineering fields to study a variety of problems, including adhesive bonding, mechanical contacts and fracture propagation. Overall, interface mechanics establishes the link between materials (or structures) bonded together by cohesive forces with various nature. In the framework of the FEM, zero-thickness interface elements have been developed, based on one-, two- and three-dimensional formulations, considering both material and geometric nonlinearities [43–45]. A comprehensive review of interesting interface models that consider the combined effect of damage, unilateral contact and friction can be found in [46].

Recently, virtual elements and interface elements have been coupled to analyze the processes of nucleation and evolution of cohesive fracture in two-dimensional bodies [47] and, also, to simulate cracking of cement-based composites [48]. In this work, we employ damage-friction IFEs to reproduce the fracture propagation phenomenon typically occurring at the intergranular zones in CMC materials beyond the elastic regime.

This study employs a two-dimensional (2D) formulation. Due to their geometric characteristics and boundary conditions, a number of significant cases can be effectively captured using 2D formulations, relying on well-considered assumptions. While three-dimensional (3D) models offer a more precise and detailed depiction of material behavior, they are often computationally demanding and complex to develop. In contrast, adopting a 2D modeling approach not only simplifies the interpretation of numerical results but also enables the execution of a large number of analyses, providing deeper insights into the material's nonlinear response [48–51]. Overall, 2D models are a good choice for qualitative intuitions, but their use should be done with caution, ensuring that appropriate geometric features and boundary conditions are valid.

It is widely recognized that identification of the RVE size is well established in periodicity-based homogenization techniques resorting to single cell concept, while it is still an opened challenge for random media [52]. These procedures are employed within limit processes involving several finite-scale continuous descriptions (Statistical Volume Elements), relative to the microstructural length scale. The solution of series of Dirichlet and Neumann boundary value problems (BVPs) at several mesoscales deduced from Hill–Mandel type macrohomogeneity condition, also valid for non-periodic and non classical media [53], provides two hierarchies of bounds for the material properties, as well as the microstructural minimal size of the RVE for performing homogenization [52,54,55].

To address this issue, we employ the Fast Statistical Homogenization Procedure (FSHP) in conjunction with the Virtual Element Method, developed by some of the authors [56,57]. This allows to rapidly determine the RVE for the CMC material operating within the framework of a first-order computational homogenization scheme. Both the equivalent elastic moduli and the characteristic size of the RVE are determined by establishing bounds on the effective response. These bounds are obtained by solving boundary value problems with either Dirichlet or Neumann boundary conditions, as discussed in [58,59], following approaches similar to those presented in [60–62] within the context of micropolar continua.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 recalls the basics of the statistical homogenization applied to the CMC material to determine the RVE size to be used in the following nonlinear analyses. Section 3 is dedicated to the model description, giving details on the virtual element and interface formulations adopted. Section 4 illustrates some benchmark tests finalized to validate the proposed modeling strategy. Section 5 investigates the response of Alumina/Zirconia RVEs focusing on the effect of the variation of microstructure and volume fraction of the two materials. Finally, concluding remarks are given in Section 6.

2. From statistical homogenization to fast statistical homogenization procedure

The main aim of this section is to recall the basics of the so-called Fast Statistical Homogenization Procedure (FSHP), already developed by some of the authors in [56,57] for particular topology, i.e. composites made of circular inclusions, representative of fibers, randomly dispersed in a second phase, called matrix. The peculiar structure of the CMC composites, characterized by random geometry of the particles besides random positions, required an ad-hoc procedure for generation of the Statistical Volume Element

Fig. 1. Neumann boundary conditions applied on the window B_δ .
Source: Modified by [32].

(SVE), as developed in [32]. Here, FSHP inspired by the pioneering works of [54,61] is adopted to determine the RVE for CMC material.

In the following, taking into account the symmetries of the tensors, in 2D framework we represent the second order tensors as 3-component vectors and the fourth order tensors as 3x3 matrices.

2.1. First order homogenization

A classical energy-based computational homogenization approach [63,64] has been adopted as a step of the Statistical Homogenization Procedure with the aim of estimating the components of the overall elastic matrix associated to random realizations of the CMC Alumina/Zirconia.

To perform the homogenization, we describe the material at two scales of interest: the microscopic and macroscopic levels. At the microscopic level, the heterogeneous material is represented in detail, accounting for all the geometric and constitutive properties of the constituents.

At the macroscopic level, the composite material is ideally replaced by an equivalent medium, whose global response is representative of that of the actual heterogeneous material. All the governing equations are known at this level and are formally the same as those defined at the microscopic level, except for the constitutive law that is not ‘a priori’ defined at the macroscopic level, but directly descends from the lower level as the result of the homogenization procedure. In the following, lower case letters are always related to the micro-scale, while upper case letters to the macro-scale.

In view of the statistical homogenization procedure, it is useful to introduce a scale parameter $\delta = L/d$ defined, at the microscopic scale, as the ratio between the edge length, L , of a square test window, and the characteristic dimension, d , of a grain.

Referring to a 2D framework, at the lower level each material phase is characterized by linear elastic isotropic behavior with the stress–strain relations written as:

$$\sigma = \mathbb{C} \epsilon \tag{1}$$

where ϵ and σ are micro-strain and micro-stress vectors, and \mathbb{C} is the elastic constitutive matrix at the microscale.

At the macroscopic level, the general anisotropic stress–strain relation reads:

$$\Sigma = \bar{\mathbb{C}} \mathbf{E} \tag{2}$$

where \mathbf{E} , Σ are the macro-strain and macro-stress vectors and $\bar{\mathbb{C}}$ is the homogenized material stiffness matrix that contains the homogenized moduli :

$$\bar{\mathbb{C}} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbb{C}}_{1111} & \bar{\mathbb{C}}_{1122} & \bar{\mathbb{C}}_{1112} \\ \bar{\mathbb{C}}_{2211} & \bar{\mathbb{C}}_{2222} & \bar{\mathbb{C}}_{2212} \\ \bar{\mathbb{C}}_{1211} & \bar{\mathbb{C}}_{1222} & \bar{\mathbb{C}}_{1212} \end{bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

i.e. the components of the macroscopic elastic matrix obtained via a homogenization procedure based on the Hill–Mandel macro-homogeneity condition [65]:

$$\mathbf{E}^T \Sigma = \frac{1}{A_\delta} \int_{B_\delta} \epsilon^T \sigma \, dA \tag{4}$$

which establishes an equivalence of the average internal work over B_δ (test window), occupying a region of area $A_\delta = \int_{B_\delta} dA$, and the mechanical internal work density of the macroscale model, expressed in terms of homogenized stress and strain measures.

The homogenization procedure is based on the solution of properly defined boundary value problems at the microscopic level with Neumann (Fig. 1) and Dirichlet (Fig. 2) boundary conditions applied on the boundary ∂B_δ , directly deriving from the fulfillment of the macro-homogeneity condition in Eq. (4).

Fig. 2. Dirichlet boundary conditions applied on the window B_δ .
Source: Modified by [32].

2.2. Fast statistical homogenization

The FSHP is based on the statistical homogenization procedure proposed in [66], then developed for micropolar continua in [61] and recently automatized in [56,57]. The procedure is conceived both for evaluating the homogenized elastic parameters of a non-periodic heterogeneous material, and identifying the RVE, which is not known a priori in the absence of a repetitive microstructure.

According to the approach presented in [52,61,67], the hypotheses of statistical homogeneity and isotropy, combined with the mean-ergodicity of the microstructure, are assumed. In this framework, the presented procedure requires the statistical definition of a number of realizations called Statistical Volume Elements (SVEs), representing the microstructure, sampled in a *Monte Carlo* sense, which allows for determining series of scale-dependent upper and lower bounds for the overall elastic moduli and to approach the RVE size, corresponding to δ_{RVE} , using a statistical stopping criterion based on the variation of the average elastic moduli.

All steps of the homogenization procedure are completely integrated in the FSHP. They are described below and schematically depicted in the flow-chart in Fig. 3.

- Step 1** Input: set the average size of the grains d and define the dimensionless scale factor $\delta = L/d$. Fix the mechanical parameters of each phase, i.e. Young's modulus and Poisson coefficient of each phase, E_i and ν_i ($i = 1,2$). Set the minimum number of simulations for convergence, N^{lim} , and a tolerance parameter, Tol , based on data dispersion.
- Step 2** Input: initialize the window size, $L = L_0$, and number of simulations, $N = N_0$.
- Step 3** Realizations: generate a random polygonal mesh with average size of grains d using the MATLAB® program PolyMesher developed by [68].
Each realization is supposed to be independent from any previous one. Based on volume fractions, mechanical parameters are randomly assigned to grains. In order to avoid *abnormal boundary layers* related to the artefact of generating the Voronoi tessellations from realizations of homogeneous random point fields created only within the considered test windows, we generate the realizations used in the numerical simulations by cutting out smaller windows. In Fig. 4, a realization obtained by FSHP for different windows sizes has been plotted, highlighting in green the cutting windows.
- Step 4** Generate/Solve: for each SVE, generate the relative mesh and solve both the Dirichlet and Neumann BVPs, and compute the homogenized constitutive parameters.
- Step 5** Compute: the homogenized bulk modulus

$$\bar{\mathbb{K}} = \left((\bar{\mathbb{C}}_{1122} + \bar{\mathbb{C}}_{2211})/2 + \bar{\mathbb{C}}_{1212} \right) / 6$$

and evaluate the average bulk modulus, $\langle \bar{\mathbb{K}} \rangle_\delta$, the relative standard deviation $S(\langle \bar{\mathbb{K}} \rangle_\delta)$ and variation coefficient $CV(\langle \bar{\mathbb{K}} \rangle_\delta)$ defined as the ratio of the standard deviation S to the mean $\bar{\mu}$ ($CV = S/\bar{\mu}$). Then, compute

$$N_i = \left(\frac{1.96 S(\langle \bar{\mathbb{K}} \rangle_\delta)}{\langle \bar{\mathbb{K}} \rangle_\delta Tol} \right)^2 \tag{5}$$

which ensures that the confidence interval of the average homogenized constitutive parameter set at 95%, evaluated over the normal standard distribution, is within the tolerance allowed, Tol . Repeat Steps 3–4 until $N_i \leq N^{lim}$. We focus our attention on the bulk modulus as a representative material parameter because the homogenized elastic tensor has mainly found to be isotropic [31,56].

- Step 6** Checking: if the number of realizations necessary to ensure the requirement at Step 5 is small enough, stop the procedure. We choose as the needed number of realizations the largest unfavorable number between those obtained by solving BVPs of Neumann or Dirichlet. Otherwise, choose an increased value of δ and go to Step 3.

Fig. 3. Flow-chart of the fast statistical homogenization procedure. Source: Adapted from [69].

Fig. 4. Example of realizations obtained by FSHP for different window size $\delta = L/d$ with in green highlighted the cutting windows. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

The fulfillment of the requirement at Step 6 means that the values of the homogenized constitutive coefficients are distributed around their averages with a vanishing variation coefficient, and that the RVE size is set. The effective homogenized elastic moduli can be determined as the arithmetic mean value between the Dirichlet (upper) and Neumann (lower) bounds at the convergence window (RVE).

The statistical convergence criterion adopted is based on a 95% confidence level of the Normal Standard distribution, which provides the number N of realizations at which it is possible to stop the simulations for a given window size δ . When this number is small enough, the average values of the effective moduli converge and the RVE size is achieved. This circumstance also corresponds

Fig. 5. Centroidal Voronoi tessellation microstructure generated via PolyMesher [68] (left) and Virtual Element extract to the mesh (right).

Fig. 6. Examples of realizations with different content of Alumina and Zirconia for window dimension $\delta = 9$ (Alumina and Zirconia grains are depicted in green and blue color, respectively). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

to reaching the minimum window size δ_{RVE} for which the estimated homogenized moduli remain constant, within a tolerance interval less than 0.5% for both the Dirichlet and Neumann solutions. The minimum number of simulations, N^{lim} , and the tolerance parameter, Tol , are chosen in order to define a narrow confidence interval for the average and obtain a reliable convergence criterion. The adopted statistical criterion allows us to detect the RVE size also when the Dirichlet and Neumann solutions do not tend to the same value. The values of the tolerance are assumed as a function of the data dispersion [61].

As already shown in [31], the geometrical features of a polycrystalline material are particularly suitable for using the Virtual Element Method as a numerical tool for solving BVPs at the microscopic scale. In this case, indeed, the microstructure can be satisfactorily modeled with a randomly generated centroidal Voronoi tessellation and it can be directly used as a computational mesh. As is well known, in fact, the recent numerical tool of the VEM permits to use single polygonal element for the grains (Fig. 5), avoiding internal meshing, with consequent significant reduction of the computational burden with respect to finite elements.

Note that at this stage, for the sake of simplicity, the average size d of grains is kept constant, but a straightforward modification to account for different sizes is possible. The computational strategies adopted are aimed at making the statistical homogenization process as efficient as possible for solving a series (hundreds) of boundary value problems, required by the statistical homogenization procedure and to rapidly converge to the RVE solution. The capability of the VEM of delivering reliable estimations of overall elastic moduli, despite the use of very coarse meshes, has been already assessed in [31,56].

2.3. Identification of Alumina/Zirconia RVE

The FSHP described is applied to identify the Alumina/Zirconia CMC material RVE, taking into account the influence of randomness of the microstructural topology. Linear elastic isotropic material is assumed for each phase, setting Young's moduli and Poisson ratios of Zirconia (Z) and Alumina (A) equal to $E_Z = 138$ GPa, $E_A = 345$ GPa, $\nu_Z = 0.28$ and $\nu_A = 0.25$, respectively [17].

Four different Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 composites are considered. These are all characterized by the average grain size $d = 0.4 \mu m$, but different volume fraction of Alumina, p , which varies in the range [20%÷80%]. Fig. 6 shows an example of realizations corresponding to the four types of material examined, when the dimensionless scale factor is $\delta = 9$.

The results of the homogenization procedure prove that the overall behavior of the composite material does not significantly differ from that of an equivalent isotropic material. Moreover, the convergence trend for the different materials depends on the different dispersion of results, as shown in Figs. 7(a)–8(a)–9(a)–10(a), where the Coefficient of Variation, CV, is plotted versus δ for Dirichlet (blue solid line) and Neumann (green solid line) solutions.

Fig. 7. Al_2O_3 $p = 20\%$. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. Al_2O_3 $p = 40\%$. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Applying the convergence criterion in Eq. (5), it emerges that results reach the convergence values at $\delta = 10$, which defines the dimension of the RVE. This is confirmed by the number of simulations needed to achieve convergence by varying the window size δ (Figs. 7(b)–8(b)–9(b)–10(b)). This result is adopted in the following nonlinear analyses.

3. Formulation of the coupled virtual element-interface element model

In this section we describe the nonlinear coupled virtual element-interface finite element model proposed. First, the governing equations of the linear elastostatic problem and its approximation using the Virtual Element Method are recalled, then, the attention is dedicated to the interface formulation.

The model is developed in the 2D framework under plane-stress assumptions and the hypothesis of small displacements and strains.

Fig. 9. Al_2O_3 $p = 60\%$. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 10. Al_2O_3 $p = 80\%$. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

3.1. Virtual element formulation

We consider a 2D domain $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ with piecewise smooth boundary $\partial\Omega$, as depicted in Fig. 11. The body is subjected to the volume force, represented by the vector $\mathbf{f} \in (L^2(\Omega))^2$, $\mathbf{f} = \{f_1, f_2\}^T$ (where $L^2(\Omega)$ is the standard Lebesgue space), and given boundary conditions, under the hypothesis of small strains. For the sake of simplicity, we consider homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions. We introduce the space of admissible displacement field, $\mathbf{V} := (H_0^1(\Omega))^2$ (with H being the Sobolev space), represented by the vector $\delta\mathbf{u}$. Furthermore, we represent the strain as the vector $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u})$ associated to the displacement field $\mathbf{u} = \{u_1, u_2\}^T$ as:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{S} \mathbf{u} \quad \text{with } \mathbf{S} = \begin{bmatrix} \partial_{x_1} & 0 \\ 0 & \partial_{x_2} \\ \partial_{x_2} & \partial_{x_1} \end{bmatrix} \tag{6}$$

where $\partial_{(\cdot)}$ denotes the partial derivative operator with respect to the (\cdot) -coordinate.

Fig. 11. Two-dimensional domain (left) and its tessellation in non overlapping polygons (right).

By using the Principle of Virtual Work it is possible to define the weak form of the linear elasto-static problem, which reads:

$$\begin{cases} \text{Find } \mathbf{u} \in \mathbf{V} \text{ such that :} \\ a(\delta \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}) = F(\delta \mathbf{u}) \quad \forall \delta \mathbf{u} \in \mathbf{V} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where

$$a(\delta \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}) = \int_{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\delta \mathbf{u})^T \mathbb{C} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}) \, d\Omega \quad (8)$$

is the continuous bi-linear form $a(\cdot, \cdot) : \mathbf{V} \times \mathbf{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Furthermore, the linear functional $F(\cdot) : \mathbf{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, reads:

$$F(\delta \mathbf{u}) = \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{f} \, d\Omega \quad (9)$$

In order to approximate the solution of the problem in Eq. (7), we consider a decomposition \mathcal{T}_h of the domain Ω into non overlapping polygonal elements E (Fig. 11). In the following, we denote by e the straight edges of the mesh \mathcal{T}_h for all $e \in \partial E$. The symbol n_e represents the number of the vertexes of the polygon E .

Let k be an integer ≥ 1 and $\mathcal{P}_k(\Omega)$ be the space of polynomials, living on the set $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$, of degree less than or equal to k .

The discrete virtual element space $\mathbf{V}_h \subseteq \mathbf{V}$ is directly defined element by element and results:

$$\mathbf{V}_h := \{ \delta \mathbf{u} \in \mathbf{V} : \delta \mathbf{u}|_E \in \mathbf{V}_{h|E} \, \forall \mathcal{T}_h \} \quad (10)$$

being $\mathbf{V}_{h|E} := [V_{h|E}]^2$ and the local space defined as follows:

$$V_{h|E} := \{ \delta u_h \in H^1(E) \cap C^0(E) : \Delta \delta u_h \in \mathcal{P}_{k-2}(E), \delta u_h|_e \in \mathcal{P}_k(e) \, \forall e \in \partial E \} \quad (11)$$

$\mathcal{P}_{k-2}(E)$ is $\{0\}$ when $k = 1$.

The space dimension $\mathbf{V}_{h|E}$ is $m = 2kn_e + k(k - 1)$. Particularly, $2n_e$ degrees of freedom are located at the vertexes of the polygon E , $2n_e(k - 1)$ degrees of freedom are located at the edges e ($2(k - 1)$ in each edge) and $k(k - 1)$ degrees of freedom are the moments defined as $\frac{1}{|E|} \int_E \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{u}_h \, dE$ for $\mathbf{q} \in (\mathcal{P}_{k-2}(E))^2$.

The definition of the local virtual element space in Eq. (11) is the classical one proposed in [20] and here adopted, but there are other possible choices [27,29]. Focusing on the definition of the local space $V_{h|E}$, it is remarked that the functions $\delta \mathbf{u}_h$ are not explicitly known inside the element but only on the element boundary.

Considering the space discretization in Eq. (10) the discrete form of the weak formulation of the problem in Eq. (7) results as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \text{Find } \mathbf{u}_h \in \mathbf{V}_h \text{ such that:} \\ a_h(\delta \mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{u}_h) = F(\delta \mathbf{u}_h) \quad \forall \delta \mathbf{u}_h \in \mathbf{V}_h \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $a_h(\cdot, \cdot) : \mathbf{V}_h \times \mathbf{V}_h \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the discrete bi-linear form approximating the continuous form $a(\cdot, \cdot)$. This is built element by element, resulting as:

$$a_h(\delta \mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{u}_h) = \sum_{E \in \mathcal{T}_h} a_h^E(\delta \mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{u}_h) \quad \forall \delta \mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{u}_h \in \mathbf{V}_h \quad (13)$$

The term $F(\delta \mathbf{u}_h)$ in Eq. (12) approximates the virtual work of the external loads.

Due to the peculiar definition of the local space \mathbf{V}_h , the evaluation of the stiffness matrix goes through the definition of the so-called projector operator Π , which is:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi : \mathbf{V}_{h|E} &\rightarrow \mathcal{P}_{k-1}(E)_{sym}^{2 \times 2} \\ \delta \mathbf{u}_h &\rightarrow \Pi(\delta \mathbf{u}_h) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Fig. 12. Schematic representation of two grains separated by a cohesive interface.

The projector operator Π represents the best approximation of the strains (in the square integral norm) in the space of piecewise polynomials of degree $k - 1$, and satisfies the following orthogonality condition:

$$\int_E \Pi(\delta \mathbf{u}_h)^T \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \, dE = \int_E \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\delta \mathbf{u}_h)^T \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \, dE \quad \forall \hat{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \in \mathcal{P}_{k-1}(E)_{sym}^{2 \times 2} \tag{15}$$

Once computed, the operator Π approximates the internal work part associated to the equilibrium weak formulation as follows:

$$a_h^E(\delta \mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{u}_h) = \int_E \Pi(\delta \mathbf{u}_h)^T \mathbb{C} \Pi(\mathbf{u}_h) \, dE + S^E(\delta \mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{u}_h) \tag{16}$$

where $S^E(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the stabilizing term, needed to preserve the coercivity of the system [19,70,71]. All the details for the construction of the stiffness matrix are available in [56,72].

In this work, the standard stabilization proposed in [19] is adopted, setting the constant $\tau = 0.5$. Furthermore, low order virtual elements with $k = 1$ are used.

3.2. Interface element formulation

3.2.1. Variational framework and constitutive law

Let A and B in Fig. 12 be two grains of the polycrystalline composite and Γ the cohesive interface between them. Under a generic loading history the grains change their configuration causing the separation of the initially overlapped upper, Γ^+ , and lower, Γ^- , sides of the interface.

The contribution of the interface to the Virtual Work of the system reads:

$$\mathcal{L} = \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{s}_{TN}^T \mathbf{t}_{TN} \, d\Gamma \tag{17}$$

where $\mathbf{s}_{TN} = \{s_T, s_N\}^T$ is the kinematic descriptor at the interface points, describing the displacement jump or gap vector, which collects the sliding, s_T , and opening, s_N , displacement jumps expressed in the interface local reference system (x_T, x_N) . This latter is identified by the tangential, x_T , and normal, x_N , directions at the interface, evaluated in its initial undeformed configuration, as shown in Fig. 12. Vector $\mathbf{t}_{TN} = \{t_T, t_N\}^T$ collects the quantities work-conjugated to \mathbf{s}_{TN} , that is the shear, t_T , and normal, t_N , tractions.

Invoking the principle of virtual displacements, the virtual variation of \mathcal{L} in Eq. (17) results as:

$$\delta \mathcal{L} = \int_{\Gamma} \delta \mathbf{s}_{TN}^T \mathbf{t}_{TN} \, d\Gamma = \int_{\Gamma} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{s}_{TN}}{\partial \mathbf{u}} \delta \mathbf{u} \right)^T \mathbf{t}_{TN} \, d\Gamma \tag{18}$$

being $\mathbf{u} = \{u_1, u_2\}^T$ the global displacement vector. The gap vector depends on the displacement \mathbf{u} . In fact, the difference of the displacements \mathbf{u}^+ and \mathbf{u}^- of the two interface overlapped faces defines the displacement jump vector as follows:

$$\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{u}^+ - \mathbf{u}^- \tag{19}$$

In Eq. (19), \mathbf{s} represents the gap vector expressed in the global reference system (x_1, x_2) . This is related to \mathbf{s}_{TN} by means of the rotation matrix \mathbf{R} , that allows the transformation from the global (x_1, x_2) to the local (x_T, x_N) reference system, i.e. $\mathbf{s}_{TN} = \mathbf{R} \mathbf{s}$.

The damage-friction nonlinear model adopted in [73–75], and based on the micromechanical approach proposed by Alfano and Sacco [76] and coupling mode I and II of failure, rules the interface constitutive response. This is based on the splitting of the representative area element linked to the typical point of the interface into an undamaged portion and a damaged one.

Fig. 13. Interface constitutive response for normal and shear modes.

Denoting with $\mathbf{C} = \text{diag}\{C_T, C_N\}$ the interface diagonal elastic stiffness matrix collecting the stiffness coefficients in the tangential, C_T , and normal, C_N , directions, respectively, and with $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ the vector accounting for all the nonlinear effects, the tractions at the interfaces result as:

$$\mathbf{t}_{TN} = \mathbf{C} (\mathbf{s}_{TN} - \boldsymbol{\pi}) \tag{20}$$

Particularly, vector $\boldsymbol{\pi} = D(\mathbf{c} + \mathbf{p})$ includes the damaging effect through the scalar damage variable D , the frictional mechanisms through vector $\mathbf{p} = \{p_T 0\}^T$ and the unilateral contact through vector $\mathbf{c} = \{0 \langle s_N \rangle_+\}^T$, being $\langle s_N \rangle_+$ the positive part of s_N . \mathbf{C} and $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ in Eq. (20) are expressed in the local reference system of the interface, though the typical subscript ‘ T_N ’ has been omitted to simplify the notation.

The damage variable D , ranging between 0 (undamaged state) and 1 (completely degraded material), evolves satisfying the thermodynamic irreversibility condition of the degrading process, i.e. $\dot{D} \geq 0$. Particularly, the evolution law is stated as:

$$D = \max_{\text{history}} \{0, \min\{1, \bar{D}\}\} \quad \text{with } \bar{D} = \frac{1}{\eta} \left(\frac{\beta}{1 + \beta} \right) \tag{21}$$

being β and η parameters computed on the basis of the relative displacements by means of the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \beta &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\langle s_N \rangle_+}{s_{N,0}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{s_T}{s_{T,0}}\right)^2} - 1 \\ \eta &= 1 - \frac{\langle s_N \rangle_+^2 \eta_N + s_T^2 \eta_T}{\langle s_N \rangle_+^2 + s_T^2} \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Quantities η_T and η_N in Eq. (22) depend on the first crack relative displacements, $s_{T,0}$ and $s_{N,0}$, as follows:

$$\eta_T = \frac{s_{T,0} t_{T,0}}{2 G_{cT}} \quad \eta_N = \frac{s_{N,0} t_{N,0}}{2 G_{cN}} \tag{23}$$

Note that the peak tractions $t_{T,0}$ and $t_{N,0}$ are associated to $s_{T,0}$ and $s_{N,0}$ by means of the elastic relationships $t_{i,0} = C_i s_{i,0}$, with $i = T, N$. Terms G_{cT} and G_{cN} in formula (23) account for the elastic and fracture energies for mode I and II of failure, as schematically depicted in Fig. 13.

Finally, the evolution of the inelastic relative displacement p_T , occurring only when damage is activated at the interface, is assumed to be governed by the classical Coulomb yield function, which depends on the friction coefficient μ [74].

To summarize, the adopted interface constitutive law accounts for nonlinear mechanisms due to the onset of tensile and shear microcracks, the re-closure of the tensile cracks in compression and the frictional phenomena. Fig. 13 shows the schematic displacement jump-traction curves, where the main parameters governing the interface response are indicated. The curves exhibit bi-linear shape in tension and shear, with the presence of softening branches and linear elastic behavior in compression.

3.2.2. Finite element formulation

The adopted interface finite element formulation considers a classical 2+2 node isoparametric element, as that depicted in Fig. 14. To describe the formulation, a notation consistent with that used in the previous section is assumed, but with capital letters to indicate quantities referred to the finite element (FE).

Let nodes 1 and 2 be on the bottom side of the interface, while nodes 3 and 4 be on the top face of the element (Fig. 14). Each node i is equipped with two translational displacement degrees of freedom, i.e. $\mathbf{U}^i = \{U_1^i U_2^i\}^T$ ($i = 1, \dots, 4$), that are all collected in the element displacement vector $\mathbf{U} = \{\mathbf{U}^{1T} \mathbf{U}^{2T} \mathbf{U}^{3T} \mathbf{U}^{4T}\}^T$.

Based on the isoparametric interpolation, the displacement jumps \mathbf{s} are approximated as follows:

$$\mathbf{s} \cong \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{NLU} \tag{24}$$

Fig. 14. Two-dimensional 2+2 node interface element.

being \mathbf{L} a kinematic operator which provides the difference between the displacements of the upper and lower interface faces and the matrix containing the interpolation functions [77]. These latter are linear functions depending on the natural coordinate of the element ξ , which varies between -1 and $+1$ defining the parent element domain (Fig. 14). As for standard interface finite element formulation, nodes geometrically coincident in the reference configuration have the same shape function, that is $N^1 = N^4 = (1-\xi)/2$ and $N^2 = N^3 = (1+\xi)/2$. This polynomial interpolation allows for a perfect coupling with the virtual elements adopted, which are based on linear approximation of the displacement fields at the element boundary.

The displacement jump vector in the local system, \mathbf{S}_{TN} , is evaluated through the rotation matrix \mathbf{R} , i.e. $\mathbf{S}_{TN} = \mathbf{R}\mathbf{S}$. Hence, the virtual variation of the internal work in Eq. (18) referred to the FE becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \mathcal{L}^e &= \int_{\Gamma^e} \delta \mathbf{S}_{TN}^T \mathbf{T}_{TN} d\Gamma^e = \delta \mathbf{U}^T \int_{\Gamma^e} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{S}_{TN}}{\partial \mathbf{U}} \right)^T \mathbf{T}_{TN} d\Gamma^e \\ &= \delta \mathbf{U}^T \underbrace{\left(\int_{\Gamma^e} \mathbf{L}^T \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{T}_{TN} d\Gamma^e \right)}_{\mathbf{F}} = \delta \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{F} \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

where \mathbf{T}_{TN} is the traction vector evaluated by using the damage-friction constitutive law described in Section 3.2.1. Note that the integral at the RHS of Eq. (25) represents the residual vector in the Newton–Raphson iterative scheme assumed to solve the nonlinear FE problem.

Accordingly, the element tangent stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} is computed by differentiation of the nodal forces \mathbf{F} as follows:

$$\mathbf{K} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}}{\partial \mathbf{U}} = \int_{\Gamma^e} \mathbf{L}^T \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{R}^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{T}_{TN}}{\partial \mathbf{U}} d\Gamma^e = \int_{\Gamma^e} \mathbf{L}^T \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{C}^t \mathbf{R} \mathbf{N} \mathbf{L} d\Gamma^e \tag{26}$$

Expression (26) has been obtained by using the chain rule differentiation to determine the derivative of the cohesive traction vector \mathbf{T}_{TN} with respect to the displacement vector \mathbf{U} . Matrix $\mathbf{C}^t = \partial \mathbf{T}_{TN} / \partial \mathbf{S}_{TN}$ is the material tangent stiffness matrix.

All the integrals over the element domain are evaluated through Gauss numerical integration procedure.

4. Modeling strategy validation

To validate the proposed modeling strategy, the tensile response of a polycrystalline RVE composed of Alumina grains is investigated assuming various interface finite element-virtual element discretizations, keeping the same microstructure. Particularly, four meshes are adopted: the first ('mesh 1' in Fig. 15) considers a single virtual element and a single interface finite element for each grain and each interface, respectively; the second and third meshes ('mesh 2' and 'mesh 3' in Fig. 15) assume increasing refinement of the interface zone; the last mesh ('mesh 4' in Fig. 15) discretizes the grains and the interfaces with multiple triangular and interface finite elements, respectively. This last mesh is selected as it permits to more accurately describe the stress and strain fields in the grains with respect to the other discretizations based on the use of low order VEs with constant stress and strain descriptions over the element domain.

The FE-VE meshes described, as well as those presented in the next paragraphs, were generated by using PolyMesher [68] in combination with an in-house Python code capable of automatically incorporating the interface elements between the Voronoi representing the grains.

Based on the results presented in Section 2.3, the RVE side is set equal to $L = 10d$, being $d = 0.4 \mu\text{m}$ the average dimension of the grains [11].

Isotropic linear elastic constitutive response is assumed for the Alumina, setting Young's modulus and Poisson ratio equal to 345 GPa and 0.25, respectively [17]. Hard connection between grains before crack developing is simulated, considering tangential and normal elastic interface stiffnesses equal to $C_T = C_N = 40 \text{ N}/\mu\text{m}^3$. Then, the nonlinear mechanisms evolve according to the parameters contained in Table 1, set on the basis of results reported in [78]. Simplifying, the grain boundary misorientation angle characteristic [79] is neglected in the definition of the interface properties.

Fig. 15. Meshes adopted to analyze the tensile response of a polycrystalline Alumina RVE.

Table 1

Nonlinear mechanical properties adopted for the interfaces.

$t_{T,0} = t_{N,0}$ [N/μm ²]	$G_{eT} = G_{eT}$ [N/μm]	μ [-]
3×10^{-4}	1×10^{-6}	0.4

Table 2

Comparison in terms of time of analysis and DOFs between Mesh 1, Mesh 2, Mesh 3 and Mesh 4 in Fig. 15, assuming interface stiffness values equal to $C_T = C_N = 40 \text{ N}/\mu\text{m}^3$ and nonlinear mechanical parameters in Table 1.

	Mesh 1	Mesh 2	Mesh 3	Mesh 4
Time of analysis	t_1	$t_2 = 2.3 t_1$	$t_3 = 8.0 t_1$	$t_4 = 2.9 t_1$
DOFs	906	1426	2210	1588

Fig. 16. Tensile response of an Alumina RVE obtained with meshes in Fig. 15: load–displacement global curves for values of the interface elastic stiffnesses equal to (a) $C_T = C_N = 40 \text{ N}/\mu\text{m}^3$ and (b) $C_T = C_N = 0.4 \text{ N}/\mu\text{m}^3$.

Uni-axial tensile loading is applied as schematically depicted in Fig. 16, that is by imposing the same increasing horizontal displacement at all nodes of the right side of the RVE, while preventing the horizontal displacements of the nodes located at the left side and avoiding the rigid body motions.

The resulting global curves, in terms of applied displacement versus total force, are shown in Fig. 16(a) for all the considered meshes. As a general trend, a good agreement emerges between the results in terms of peak load and slope of the softening branches, despite a slight difference can be detected for the curve derived with mesh 1 in the zone of the vanishing force. In fact, Fig. 17, which compares the RVE deformed configurations derived with all meshes, shows that the RVE separation is not yet complete at the value of the imposed displacement equal to $0.007 \mu\text{m}$ only in the case of mesh 1. However, the overall nonlinear response is efficiently captured by the coarsest FE-VE discretization with computational cost saving, as proved by data collected in Table 2. This latter reports the number of degrees of freedom (DOFs) characterizing each mesh and compares the corresponding computational time, assuming as reference value that associated to mesh 1, that is denoted with t_1 .

Fig. 17. Tensile response of an Alumina RVE obtained with meshes in Fig. 15 assuming $C_T = C_N = 40 \text{ N}/\mu\text{m}^3$: deformed configurations (scale factor equal to 100) at the imposed displacement equal to $0.007 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 18. Tensile response of an Alumina RVE obtained with meshes in Fig. 15 assuming $C_T = C_N = 0.4 \text{ N}/\mu\text{m}^3$: deformed configurations (scale factor equal to 100) at the imposed displacement equal to $0.01 \mu\text{m}$.

The reliability of the proposed modeling strategy is also investigated considering different mechanical properties of the joints. Hence, the tensile response of the Alumina RVE is studied by assuming modified values of the elastic tangential and normal interface stiffnesses, that is $C_T = C_N = 0.4 \text{ N}/\mu\text{m}^3$, but the same tensile and shear peak tractions, fracture energies and friction coefficient previously adopted. Consequently, this set of parameters allows higher grain separation displacements before crack onset.

The corresponding load–displacement global curves, derived with meshes in Fig. 15, are reported in Fig. 16(b). As expected, these exhibit lower initial elastic stiffness with respect to the previous case, but, also, a reduced maximum load. The dashed branches are introduced into the curves at the sudden force drop, as possible snap-back behavior could be detected if other solution strategies, such as the Arc-Length Method, were applied.

The cracking paths in Fig. 18 show a fracture passing from the top to the bottom side of the RVE that causes the specimen separation in two parts, regardless the FE-VE discretization adopted, thus further proving the accuracy and efficiency of the proposed modeling approach.

Finally, a shear test is investigated. As schematically represented in Fig. 19, all nodes of the upper side of the RVE are subjected to the same horizontal displacement, gradually increasing during the analysis, while keeping fixed the nodes on the bottom side. The corresponding global curves, relating the applied displacement to the total force, are shown in Fig. 19 for the case $C_T = C_N = 40 \text{ N}/\mu\text{m}^3$, selected as example. It is evident that almost identical results are derived for all the meshes studied. The initial elastic phase is followed by a nonlinear branch up to the peak load. Then, a softening branch appears without sudden drops of the force. In fact, the failure mechanism involves the progressive formation of a horizontal crack band at the base, where the tensile stresses at the interfaces are concentrated: intergranular debonding progressively occurs inducing a sort of clockwise overturning of the upper part of the specimen. The overall failure mechanism is ruled by opening of the interfaces (see Fig. 20).

5. Response of Alumina/Zirconia composites

In this section, the mechanical behavior of a two-phase polycrystalline material is studied. Particularly, the response of Alumina/Zirconia ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2$) RVEs is analyzed, focusing on the fracture process caused by tensile and shear loads. First, the effect of different volume fractions of the two material components is studied; then, assuming a fixed percentage of Alumina, the influence of shape and distribution of grains is investigated.

Mechanical parameters of Zirconia and Alumina are assumed as in Section 2.3, that is $E_Z = 138 \text{ GPa}$, $E_A = 345 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_Z = 0.28$ and $\nu_A = 0.25$, respectively.

As for the interaction behavior between the crystals, a simplified hypothesis is applied, consisting in the assumption of the same mechanical properties for all the interface elements regardless of the type of grains, Alumina or Zirconia, connected. Stiff interfaces are assumed with $C_T = C_N = 40 \text{ N}/\mu\text{m}^3$ and Table 1 is referenced for the nonlinear mechanical parameters.

Similarly to the scenarios analyzed previously, in all simulations the RVE size is set equal to $L = 10 d$, being $d = 0.4 \mu\text{m}$ the average dimension of the grains. Moreover, relying on the modeling approach proposed in this work and the numerical evidences discussed in Section 4, coarse VE-FE meshes are employed in the analyses, thus discretizing each grain and each interface with a single virtual element and a single interface element, respectively.

Fig. 19. Shear test on Alumina RVE using meshes in Fig. 15: load–displacement global curves for values of the interface elastic stiffnesses equal to $C_T = C_N = 40 \text{ N}/\mu\text{m}^3$.

Fig. 20. Shear test on Alumina RVE using meshes in Fig. 15 and assuming $C_T = C_N = 40 \text{ N}/\mu\text{m}^3$: deformed configurations (scale factor equal to 10) at the imposed displacement equal to $0.03 \mu\text{m}$.

5.1. Effect of volume fraction of the materials

The Alumina/Zirconia specimens shown in Fig. 21 are characterized by the same shape and position of grains, but different percentage p of the Alumina content, that is $p = 0, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100\%$. Percentage p is evaluated in terms of volume fraction of the Alumina with respect to the whole composite. Note that the selected particle geometry and distribution differ from that above analyzed.

The uni-axial tensile behavior is investigated by performing displacement-controlled analyses under the same loading and boundary conditions described in Section 4. The resulting response curves, reported in Fig. 22 with reference to all percentages p , exhibit similar peak loads but different slopes of the initial elastic branches, as a consequence of the distinct elastic properties of the constituents. The post-peak responses clearly differ, the softening branches being steeper moving from $p = 100\%$ to $p = 0\%$. Also in this case, dashed branches are introduced to account for the presence of possible snap-back phenomenon.

To be noted is that the main features of the global curves are related to how the fractures arise and propagate during the loading history. This is clearly highlighted in Fig. 23, which contains the scaled deformed configuration of each RVE at the last step of the analyses. For the lower values of p , that is $p = 0, 20, 40, 60\%$, a main crack passing from the top to the bottom side of the RVE develops, although this has a different location as p varies. Conversely, two significant cracks appear in the cases of $p = 80\%$ and $p = 100\%$, making the cracking path more intricate and, thus, postponing the complete failure of the RVEs.

Finally, two fracture propagation processes are shown in Fig. 24, referring to the limit cases of $p = 0\%$ and $p = 100\%$. In particular, the distributions of the damage variable D (defined in Eq. (21)) at the interfaces are plotted in correspondence of various steps of the analyses, indicated by points A, B, C, D, E, F and G in Fig. 22. The first significant crack always arises at the interface located in the middle bottom part of the RVE (see point A and E), but, then, the cracking path evolves differently, leading to a localized fracture in case of $p = 0\%$ and to a more widespread damage state in case of $p = 100\%$.

Fig. 21. Alumina/Zirconia RVEs with different percentages p of Alumina.

Fig. 22. Tensile response of Alumina/Zirconia RVEs with different percentages of Alumina: load–displacement global curves.

5.2. Effect of microstructure

The effect of the grain shape and distribution, strictly connected to the randomness characteristic of the microstructure, is here investigated considering the three specimens depicted in Fig. 25. These are characterized by the microstructures denoted as ‘G1’, ‘G2’ and ‘G3’, but same Alumina volume fraction $p = 60\%$. Note that microstructure G1 corresponds to that studied in Section 5.1.

Assuming the loading and boundary conditions described in detail in Section 4, Figs. 26 and 27 show the uni-axial tensile response of the specimens in terms of load–displacement global curves and deformed configurations, respectively. The curves exhibit similar peak loads and slope of the softening branches but, also, some discrepancies due to the occurring stress distributions that induce different localizations of the main crack.

Finally, the investigation is moved to another loading scenario. The assumed loading and boundary conditions correspond to those detailed in Section 4 for the shear test. These completely restrain the base of the specimens and impose an increasing horizontal displacement at all nodes of their top side.

Fig. 23. Tensile response of Alumina/Zirconia RVEs with different percentages of Alumina: cracks at the end of the analyses (scale factor of the deformed configuration equal to 100).

Fig. 24. Tensile response of Alumina and Zirconia RVEs: distributions of the damage variable, D , at the interfaces in correspondence of points A, B, C, D, E, F and G indicated in Fig. 22.

The resulting global curves (Fig. 28) show very similar features with no sudden drops of the force. In fact, for all the tested microstructures, the fracture process starts at the bottom left corner, where the maximum tensile stresses at the interfaces are concentrated, and, then, gradually spreads around crossing the entire RVE and inducing its collapse (Fig. 29).

6. Conclusions

This work aimed to propose a computationally efficient modeling approach for the analysis of the fracture propagation in polycrystalline composites with thin interfaces or grain boundaries. The model exploits in a combined way the advantages of the modern and appealing Virtual Element Method and the consolidate Finite Element Method.

The key idea is to discretize each crystal with a single virtual element and model the interaction behavior between the particles by means of a mesh composed of interface finite elements, where the damaging and frictional phenomena are assumed to be concentrated. This allows to capture the typical failure mechanism due to the intergranular fractures avoiding the dense FE discretizations usually employed.

Fig. 25. Alumina/Zirconia RVEs with percentage of Alumina equal to $p = 60\%$ and different microstructures G1, G2 and G3.

Fig. 26. Tensile response of Alumina/Zirconia RVEs with percentage of Alumina equal to $p = 60\%$ and different microstructures: load–displacement global curves.

Fig. 27. Tensile response of Alumina/Zirconia RVEs with percentage of alumina equal to $p = 60\%$ and different microstructures: cracks at the end of the analyses (scale factor of the deformed configuration equal to 100).

The modeling strategy is actually applicable to many categories of composites, with random or periodic microstructure. In this work, the attention was dedicated to the study of the micromechanical response of CMC representative volume elements, with special focus on the paradigmatic example of Alumina/Zirconia composites.

The main contributions and novelty of the paper can be listed as follows:

- the coupled use of virtual elements and interface elements has been applied for the first time to the modeling of CMC materials in the nonlinear field to track intergranular fracture propagation;
- the developed formulation allows for significant mesh flexibility with low computational cost, as the admissible virtual elements are polygons of any shape, possibly characterized by hanging nodes, that well mimic the shape of particles of polycrystalline composites;

Fig. 28. Shear test on Alumina/Zirconia RVEs with percentage of Alumina equal to $p = 60\%$ and different microstructures: load–displacement global curves.

Fig. 29. Shear test on Alumina/Zirconia RVEs with percentage of Alumina equal to $p = 60\%$ and different microstructures: cracks at the end of the analyses (scale factor of the deformed configuration equal to 10).

- the Fast Statistical Homogenization Technique proposed in [32,56] has been applied to select in reasonable manner the RVE of the random media analyzed;
- the campaign of comparative analyses performed, involving tensile and shear tests, proved the reliability of the proposed approach and allowed to trace comparisons also between VEM and FEM computations. Results derived from coarse meshes, where the interface between grains is modeled with a single interface FE and each crystal is represented with a single VE, well represent those obtained using denser discretizations for grains and interfaces, with a maximum computational saving of approximately 87% in terms of analysis time;
- the numerical simulations performed on Alumina/Zirconia RVEs highlighted the effects of the main factors affecting the response of these composites, i.e. the variation of the volume fraction of the material components and that of the microstructure. It emerged that, as the Zirconia content increases, a more brittle tensile response occurs with the load–displacement global curves exhibiting more severe softening branches. As for the influence of the microstructure, the response curves exhibit similar peak loads and slope of the softening branches, though different cracking paths occur under tensile loads in the analyzed cases.

To summarize, the model appears as an efficient numerical tool for analyzing response of composite materials characterized by different representative size of the microstructure. For instance, this could be embedded in a multiscale procedure for the analysis of polycrystalline materials with nanoscale size grains randomly distributed. In this framework, the constitutive response of the homogeneous material considered at the macroscopic level could be derived by the step-by-step detailed analysis of the RVE identified through the FSHP [32,56] and modeled with the VE-FE formulation presented. Moreover, the FSHP could be extended to the nonlinear range, so that to evaluate the mechanical properties of the structural-scale material with an a-priori RVE-based homogenization.

The model can be further improved by adopting advanced virtual element formulations accounting for enhanced description of the strain field leading to a self-stabilized elements [27,29]. Moreover, higher order continua, such as Couple-Stress and Cosserat, could be adopted for the grain description, as these have proved to better represent the behavior of microstructured material with random particles having different shape and orientation [80].

Finally, the decrease of the number of degrees of freedom offered by the use of coarse VE-meshes makes the adopted modeling strategy attractive to model real case microstructures.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Cristina Gatta: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Marco Pingaro:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Daniela Addressi:** Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Patrizia Trovalusci:** Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Patrizia Trovalusci reports financial support was provided by University of Rome La Sapienza. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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